

Mind the Prompt: A Novel Benchmark for Prompt-based Class-Agnostic Counting

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Abstract

Recently, object counting has shifted towards class-agnostic counting (CAC), which counts instances of arbitrary object classes never seen during model training. With advancements in robust vision-and-language foundation models, there is a growing interest in prompt-based CAC, where object categories are specified using natural language. However, we identify significant limitations in current benchmarks for evaluating this task, which hinder both accurate assessment and the development of more effective solutions. Specifically, we argue that the current evaluation protocols do not measure the ability of the model to understand which object has to be counted. This is due to two main factors: (i) the shortcomings of CAC datasets, which primarily consist of images containing objects from a single class, and (ii) the limitations of current counting performance evaluators, which are based on traditional class-specific counting and focus solely on counting errors. To fill this gap, we introduce the Prompt-Aware Counting (PrACo) benchmark. It comprises two targeted tests coupled with evaluation metrics specifically designed to quantitatively measure the robustness and trustworthiness of existing prompt-based CAC models. We evaluate state-of-the-art methods and demonstrate that, although some achieve impressive results on standard class-specific counting metrics, they exhibit a significant deficiency in understanding the input prompt, indicating the need for more careful training procedures or revised designs. The code for reproducing our results is available at <https://github.com/ciampluca/PrACo>.

1. Introduction

Class-agnostic counting (CAC) aims to count instances of arbitrary objects beyond the set of categories seen at

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Figure 1. Prompt-based counting models – CounTX [2] in this example – exhibit difficulties in accurately interpreting user-provided texts that specify object classes to be counted. The confusion occurs even between classes that are semantically very distinct – like *marbles* and *elephants*. In some cases, the count of classes not present in the image is even higher than that for the ground-truth object category (highlighted in orange).

training [25]. This emerging trend overcomes the limitations affecting long-standing class-specific counting methods, which require individually trained networks for each object type – e.g., people [4, 10, 13, 20, 26, 28], vehicles [1, 7, 33], or cells [5, 6, 9, 22]. In contrast, CAC draws inspiration from humans’ instinctive ability to discern what merits counting when confronted with unfamiliar objects, and it enables users to specify arbitrary categories of interest at inference time without needing model retraining or new annotated data.

Target object classes in CAC can be specified by users

with visual exemplars, *i.e.*, bounding boxes surrounding object samples in the image [11, 19, 29, 31, 32], or with text prompts, *i.e.*, textual object descriptions [2, 14, 15, 18, 23, 27, 30]. Techniques leveraging visual exemplars currently outperform prompt-based methods, as exemplars offer more detailed information than text, providing inherent information about the visual appearance of the objects. Nevertheless, prompt-based methods enhance flexibility and improve the capabilities and generality of counting models requiring reduced human intervention – humans do not have to specify bounding boxes as input. These methods leverage the models’ natural language understanding and work hand-in-hand with popular vision-language foundation models such as CLIP [24], thus representing highly appealing solutions [2, 23].

However, in this paper, we figured out that current benchmarks exploited for assessing prompt-based CAC approaches are affected by severe limitations hampering their proper evaluation and the development of new, more performing solutions. As shown in Fig. 1, we empirically verified that some state-of-the-art prompt-based CAC approaches are not always able to truly understand *which* object class has to be counted from the textual description. In contrast, they tend to count object instances belonging to the predominant class despite the prompt meaning. This is a critical failure in real-world scenarios if we imagine that such systems are usually deployed to count specific objects – *e.g.*, imagine a surveillance scenario in which the officer wants to count the number of pedestrians transiting on the street, but at that moment, only cars are present. We argue that this lack relies on two key factors: (i) the shortcomings affecting the main CAC datasets and (ii) the limitations affecting current counting performance evaluators. Specifically, most of the samples making up the CAC datasets contain objects belonging to a single class, making it hard to evaluate the model’s robustness to discriminate different object classes within an image. Furthermore, the metrics exploited for measuring the performance of CAC models are inherited from class-specific counting and do not consider some key factors of prompt-based CAC, focusing only on the counting error and disregarding assessing the model’s trustworthiness to understand the object category described by the textual prompt.

In this work, we propose Prompt-Aware Counting (PrACo), a novel benchmark designed to quantitatively evaluate the robustness and trustworthiness of prompt-based CAC approaches, tackling the two above-mentioned limitations. The benchmark includes two tailored tests coupled with ad-hoc evaluation metrics: (i) a *negative-label* test, which probes single-class images by using prompts that refer to absent classes, and (ii) a *mosaic* test, which evaluates artificially created mosaicked images built by stitching together pairs of single-class images, where one

object category serves as a distractor to the category described by the textual prompt. To validate our new benchmark, we assess several recent SOTA prompt-based CAC techniques, and we show that some of them show a notable weakness in understanding the object class textual descriptions despite achieving top performance on standard class-specific metrics. This highlights the necessity for more refined training procedures or reconsideration of their architectural designs.

To summarize, we propose the following contributions:

- We empirically figured out that the evaluation of state-of-the-art prompt-based class-agnostic counting methods is limited by current datasets and metrics, hindering the development of more effective solutions.
- We propose PrACo, a novel benchmark that introduces a set of ad-hoc evaluation protocols and associated metrics to evaluate the robustness and trustworthiness of existing CAC models to count objects belonging to classes described with natural language.
- We exploit PrACo to show that many recent state-of-the-art methods exhibit a remarkable deficiency in understanding objects to be counted, although achieving top results in standard class-specific counting metrics.

2. Related Work

2.1. Class-specific Object Counting

Object counting is one of the core tasks in computer vision due to its widespread applicability to many real-world applications. Thus, many methods have been proposed to count specific object categories, such as people [4, 13, 20, 26, 28], cars [1, 7, 33], insects [3, 8], or cells [6, 9]. Approaches that regress and sum density maps have emerged to be more accurate in crowded scenarios [3, 4, 13, 20, 26, 28] than techniques relying on prior detection of object instances [1, 7]. Either way, the main drawback of these methods lies in requiring individually trained networks and, consequently, labeled datasets for each object type.

2.2. Prompt-based Class-agnostic Counting

Recently, class-agnostic counting (CAC) has generalized object counting to open-world settings, where users can specify arbitrary object classes never seen during model training by exploiting (i) visual exemplars, *i.e.*, bounding boxes around the objects of interest within the same input image [11, 19, 29, 31, 32], or (ii) textual prompts, *i.e.*, natural-language descriptions of the object class [2, 14, 15, 18, 23, 27, 30]. The first setting provides the best performance: methods such as CACViT [29], SSD [31], CounTR [19], LOCA [11], and SAFECount [32] reach state-of-the-art in all CAC benchmarks. In contrast,

prompt-based CAC approaches are particularly appealing since they enhance overall flexibility even if they achieve lower performance.

Most of the SOTA prompt-based CAC approaches rely on vision-language foundation models that map text-image pairs to a joint embedding space. The produced features are then passed to a decoder in charge of producing density maps. The authors in [30] trained a conditional variational autoencoder (VAE) based on the popular CLIP model [24] to generate visual exemplar prototypes conditioned with their semantic embedding encoded in the provided category name. Concurrently, [2] proposed CounTX that instead is trained end-to-end and produces object counts directly, skipping the intermediate visual exemplar proposal step. Being based on CLIP to measure the similarity between image patches and class descriptions, it also accepts a more detailed specification of the target object to count (rather than simply using a class name). Similarly, CLIP-Count [14] relies on CLIP to align the text embedding with dense visual features. However, the authors also designed a hierarchical patch-text interaction module to propagate semantic information across different resolution levels of visual features. Another similar CLIP-based model trained end-to-end is VLCounter [15]. Here, the authors incorporated three modules to efficiently finetune CLIP for the counting task and to exploit intermediate features across different encoding layers of CLIP in the decoding stage. Very recently, DAVE [23] proposed a two-stage detect-and-verify paradigm. In the first stage, they estimate a high-recall set of candidate detections, which are then analyzed and filtered in the second verification step, relying on unsupervised clustering and CLIP embedding. Differently from the above-described architectures, TFPOC [27] employed a detection-based technique, leveraging the popular SAM [16] for instance segmentation. The authors proposed a two-stage approach. In the first stage, they exploited CLIP-Surgery [17], an enhanced version of CLIP, to produce visual exemplar prototypes by computing the similarity between images and text representations. In the second step, they computed a similarity map between image features and the masks corresponding to the reference objects produced by SAM prompted with the bounding boxes from the first stage.

All of these prompt-based methods derive from the literature on exemplar-based CAC, where elements to be counted are chosen by selecting some exemplars from the given image. As a result, prompt-based CAC methods also assume the object is present in the image. Our goal is to test a scenario where this assumption is relaxed, allowing for the possibility that (i) the object may not be present in the image, (ii) the image may contain more than one object class, or even (iii) the user provides a misleading or ambiguous query. We empirically demonstrate that prompt-based CAC models are activated by non-present categories and, there-

fore, are unable to truly understand object categories to be counted from textual descriptions.

2.3. Dataset and Metrics

The gold standard dataset for CAC is FSC-147 [25]. It contains 6,135 images across 147 object categories, with 89 categories used for training, 29 for validation, and 29 for testing, with no class overlap between these subsets. Annotations consist of dots over the approximate centroids of each object instance, as usual for the counting task – ground truth density maps are created by superimposing Gaussian kernels centered on these dots. Furthermore, the authors provided three bounding boxes per image that localize the exemplars and the natural language name of the object category to which they belong – the category is unique for each image, and it has been chosen arbitrarily if multiple categories were present. However, cases in which multiple object categories are present in the same image are just a few, and this represents an inherent limitation of FSC-147, making it hard to evaluate the model’s robustness to discriminate different object classes within an image. To address this shortcoming, two other datasets have been proposed: OmniCount-191 [21] and MCAC [12]. These datasets include multiple object categories within the same images. However, the first one is not publicly available, while MCAC lacks suitable annotations for prompt-based approaches.

Standard counting metrics in the literature are the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean squared error (RMSE), defined as $MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |\tilde{c}_n - c_n|$ and $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\tilde{c}_n - c_n)^2}$, where N is the number of test images, and \tilde{c}_n and c_n are the ground truth and predicted counts, respectively. Another performance evaluator, used less frequently, is represented by the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), which is essentially a normalized MAE and is defined as $MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{|\tilde{c}_n - c_n|}{\tilde{c}_n}$. However, these evaluators were inherited from the class-specific counting task and exhibit severe limitations particularly evident in prompt-based CAC. Specifically, they do not take into account *which* object category has to be counted nor the model’s ability to understand the provided textual prompt.

3. The PrACo Benchmark

3.1. Overview

We assume to have a collection of N tuples $\mathcal{X} = \{(I_1, P_1), (I_2, P_2), \dots, (I_N, P_N)\}$, where I_i is an image and P_i is the class name of the objects within I_i , *i.e.*, the description of the object class present in it. Thus, each image contains objects belonging to only a single class.

We define P_i as the *positive* class and all the $\{P_j\}_{j \neq i}$ as the *negative* classes for the given image I_i . Without loss of

Figure 2. Inference schemas for the *negative-label test* (on the left) and the *mosaic test* (on the right). The numbers reported in the boxes show the ideal model outcomes: for the negative-label test, the diagonal of the shown matrix should be filled with the ground-truth object counts and with zeros elsewhere; for the mosaic test, each mosaic outcome should contain the ground-truth counts on the top – which is the same for each row of the shown matrix – and zeros on the bottoms. In the dotted boxes on the bottom, we report a schema of the inference procedures needed for computing each entry of the two matrices.

generality, we also assume that each class is represented by only one image in the dataset, even though, in real-world scenarios, datasets typically contain multiple images of the same object class. Finally, we assume to have a prompt-based CAC model $\mathcal{M}(I, P)$, which takes as input a generic image I together with an arbitrary prompt P and outputs an estimated count c of the object instances belonging to the object class described by P . In this setting, PrACo introduces two test suites, which are detailed in the following sections: (i) a *negative-label test* and (ii) a *mosaic test*.

3.2. Negative-label test

The *negative-label test* evaluates single-class images by prompting the model with textual descriptions referring to absent object classes. Formally, for all the elements $\{I_i, P_j\}_{i,j=1}^N$, we compute $c_{ij} = \mathcal{M}(I_i, P_j)$ to obtain the predicted count for each image when prompted with all the available class descriptions in the dataset. The optimal test outcome can be formalized as follows:

$$c_{ij} = \begin{cases} \tilde{c}_i, & \text{if } i = j \\ 0, & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where \tilde{c}_i is the ground truth count for the image I_i .

The ideal situation is illustrated in the left part of Fig. 2. Intuitively, standard class-specific counting metrics consider only the count predictions concerning the positive class – the orange diagonal in the matrix of Fig. 2. Con-

versely, we account for the count predictions concerning the negative classes – the remaining non-diagonal elements in the matrix of Fig. 2. To quantitatively assess this test, we introduce two ad-hoc metrics.

Normalized Mean of Negative predictions (NMN).

NMN is the absolute counting error computed by prompting the model with the negative classes, normalized by the ground truth of the positive class. It is computed as follows (more details in the supplementary material):

$$\text{NMN} = \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\tilde{c}_i} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N c_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Notice that the reason for normalizing the average of the negative counts by the ground truth of the positive class is given by the assumption that having more items in the image also causes the model to increase the estimate of non-present classes. Therefore, the normalization factor $1/\tilde{c}_i$ plays the role of relativizing the error – in other words, we suppose that counting 10 *dogs* in an image showing 1000 *people* is a negligible error. The lower the NMN value, the better the resulting model.

Positive Class Count Nearness (PCCN).

PCCN mixes positive and negative class predictions, providing an overall quantitative assessment of strong failures in the model.

Formally, it is defined as follows:

$$\text{PCCN} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{I}(d_i^{\text{pos}} < d_i^{\text{neg}}) \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

where $d_i^{\text{neg}} = |\frac{1}{N} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N c_{ij} - \tilde{c}_i|$ is the absolute difference between the mean of the model’s negative classes predictions and the ground truth for the i -th image, $d_i^{\text{pos}} = |c_{ii} - \tilde{c}_i|$ is the absolute difference between the model’s positive class prediction and the ground truth count for the i -th image, and $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is an indicator function, which equals 1 if the condition inside it is true, and 0 otherwise. Thus, PCCN measures the percentage of data samples for which the model produces a positive class count estimate that is closer to the ground truth compared to the mean of the negative class count estimations. Intuitively, a mean of the negative class estimations that is closer to the ground truth than a positive class estimate may indicate that the model is strongly biased toward counting negative classes over the positive class, which in turn may be due to the model completely losing the semantics of the given prompt. It follows that the higher the PCCN, the better the resulting model.

3.3. Mosaic test

The *mosaic* test assesses images containing multiple object categories by providing the model with textual prompts referring only to the positive class, emulating very common real-case scenarios. Thus, the object instances belonging to the negative classes serve as distractors to the positive class. To overcome the lack of suitable annotated CAC datasets having multi-class images, we artificially build a new set of such images. Specifically, starting from existing single-class CAC datasets, we create mosaicked images by stitching together pairs of positive and negative single-class images, similarly to [2].

Formally, we consider all the possible pairs of images $\{I_i, I_j\}_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N$, and the positive class P_i of the image I_i . We call I_i and I_j the *positive* and the *negative* images, respectively. We create new mosaicked images $I_{ij}^{\text{mosaic}} = \text{vstack}(I_i, I_j)$ by vertically stitching together the positive image, placed at the top, with the negative one, placed at the bottom. Then, the CAC model \mathcal{M} is tasked to predict the following quantities concerning the positive class P_i :

$$c_{ij}^{\text{pos}}, c_{ij}^{\text{neg}} = \mathcal{M}(I_{ij}^{\text{mosaic}}, P_i), \quad (4)$$

where c_{ij}^{pos} and c_{ij}^{neg} are the positive and negative class counts relative to the top and the bottom parts of the mosaic, respectively. This can be easily obtained from most density-based models, as it is sufficient to cut the output density map in half along the y-axis and integrate them separately to obtain the respective positive and negative counts. It is

worth noting that negative images influence not only the negative class count c_{ij}^{neg} , but also the positive class count c_{ij}^{pos} . Indeed, the goal of this test is to evaluate the robustness of the model to count the positive class described by the prompt in the presence of distractors, *i.e.*, objects from different categories within the same image. Similarly to the negative-label test, we ideally want c_{ij}^{pos} to converge to the ground truth count, while c_{ij}^{neg} should ideally approach zero. This means the model (i) should not be distracted by negative examples when attending to positive instances, and (ii) should refrain from counting any negative instances in the mosaic. We summarize this inference procedure in the right part of Fig. 2.

Since each mosaic includes both positive and negative instances, this test bears similarities to object detection evaluation, where both correct and incorrect detections can occur, and performance is typically assessed using *precision*, which reflects the proportion of correct predictions among all model outputs, and *recall*, which represents the percentage of correct instances retrieved from the total ground-truth. However, differently from object detection, in our scenario, we do not have clear indications about the correctness of each proposed instance, given that we do not know – and we are not requested to know – precise instance localization within the image, as we are only interested in the final aggregated count for the provided object class. Such information could be partially recovered from the two output counts c_{ij}^{pos} and c_{ij}^{neg} by making some reasonable assumptions that we present in the following, where we introduce precision-recall metrics shaped for prompt-based CAC.

Counting Precision (CntP) and Counting Recall (CntR).

Classical precision and recall metrics used in detection scenarios are defined through true positive count (TP), false positive count (FP), and false negative count (FN). In the counting scenario, we do not have an indication of whether a single instance is correct or not, as we only have the estimated global count for the provided class of objects. We only know that correct objects are only present in the positive image I_i and that the negative image I_j only contains incorrect examples for the prompt P_i . To adapt precision and recall metrics to the counting case, we make a simple assumption. Specifically, for the counting contributions c_{ij}^{pos} from the positive image I_i , we never have FN instances. We may only have FPs in the case where the predicted count $c_{ij}^{\text{pos}} > \tilde{c}_i$, where \tilde{c}_i is the ground truth count for the positive instances in I_i . In such a case, we are assuming that the instances exceeding the correct count are false predictions. Also note that all the contributions c_{ij}^{neg} coming from the negative image I_j are surely FPs, as in such cases, the model is erroneously counting the incorrect instances in the lower part of the mosaic. Figure 3 shows an example of the computation of TPs and FPs for adapting the precision and

Figure 3. Example of the derivation of TPs and FPs in the mosaic scenario. In the shown case where the model predicts $c^{\text{pos}} = 3$ and $c^{\text{neg}} = 20$, the number of estimated true positives is bounded to the ground-truth value (15). The remaining 5 counted elements are considered false positives from the positive image ($\text{FP}^{\text{pos}} = 5$), which are then merged with the false positives from the negative image ($\text{FP}^{\text{neg}} = c^{\text{neg}} = 3$), to obtain a total of 8 FPs.

recall detection metrics to the counting scenario.

Under the above considerations and assumptions, we obtain that *counting precision* (CntP) and *counting recall* (CntR) can be defined as follows:

$$\text{CntP} = \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N \frac{\min(c_{ij}^{\text{pos}}, \tilde{c}_i)}{c_{ij}^{\text{pos}} + c_{ij}^{\text{neg}}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{CntR} = \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N \frac{\min(c_{ij}^{\text{pos}}, \tilde{c}_i)}{\tilde{c}_i} \quad (6)$$

We refer the reader to the supplementary material for the derivation of such expressions from the idea in Fig. 3.

The *counting recall* metric is useful to understand if the model can correctly estimate the number of objects belonging to the positive class. Interestingly, in the range $c_{ij}^{\text{pos}} < \tilde{c}_i$, it correlates negatively with the MAPE error metric – clamping to 1 when the predicted count is greater than the ground truth. Therefore, CntR carries information partially correlated with class-specific counting metrics, except that the model is also exposed to negative examples that may alter the number of predicted instances.

Differently, the *counting precision* metric is useful to understand if the model is erroneously including in the count estimation also objects belonging to classes not specified by the textual prompt and present in the negative image I_j . Specifically, it is sensitive to the FPs found both in the positive image I_i – the counting excess with respect to the ground-truth – and in the negative image I_j – where every instance is considered a FP.

Counting Balanced F1-score (CntF1). A common way to aggregate precision and recall to obtain a single indicator

is the F1-score, which is defined as the harmonic mean of the two metrics. We therefore derive a *counting F1-score* (CntF1) indicator, as follows:

$$\text{CntF1} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{CntP} \cdot \text{CntR}}{\text{CntP} + \text{CntR}} \quad (7)$$

This metric is useful for comparing the overall performance of the CAC models, taking into consideration objects belonging both to desired and undesired classes.

4. Experimental Evaluation

4.1. Dataset and Methods

Dataset. Our benchmark relies on FSC-147 [25], a widely used dataset for CAC containing 6,135 images with objects belonging to 147 classes. Labels include dots over the object centroids, bounding boxes for three object exemplars, and object category textual names (see also Sec. 2). Although most images contain objects belonging to a single category, we filter out the few multi-class images by following the approach in [23]. This prevents interferences with our proposed tests, ensuring that no false positives arise from other object classes present in the same image.

Probed Methods. We place under the spotlight six different state-of-the-art prompt-based CAC methods: CounTX [2], CLIP-Count [14], TFPOC [27], VL-Counter [15], and DAVE [23]. Specifically, CounTX, CLIP-Count, and VLCounter directly estimate density-maps end-to-end by fine-tuning CLIP and conditioning the density-map generation on the CLIP embedding of the desired object class. Instead, TFPOC and DAVE employ two-stage approaches that detect all the objects in the image and then filter them based on the input textual prompt.

Implementation Details. We employed the original code and pre-trained models provided by the authors, maintaining their image pre-processing pipelines, hyperparameters, and prompting schema. We only needed to adjust the DAVE inference procedure to behave correctly on our benchmark. In the supplementary material, we provide further details on these changes along with the PrACo performance of the original DAVE implementation.

4.2. Results

Quantitative Results on Negative and Mosaic Tests.

We report the results for both the test and validation splits in Tab. 1 and Tab. 2, respectively. As we can notice, although the methods achieve remarkable performance on standard counting error measures (MAE and RMSE), the outcome is quite heterogeneous on the PrACo metrics. Notably, the negative test on one-stage methods like CounTX,

Table 1. Results on the **test set** of FSC147 on both PrACo metrics (negative and mosaics tests) and on classic metrics.

Method	Negative Test		Mosaic Test			Classic	
	NMN ↓	PCCN ↑	CntP ↑	CntR ↑	CntF1 ↑	MAE ↓	RMSE ↓
CounTX [2] (BMVC '23)	0.95	64.51	0.686	0.712	0.630	15.92	106.89
CLIP-Count [14] (ACM MM '23)	1.27	38.13	0.495	0.761	0.554	17.59	109.97
VLCounter [15] (AAAI '24)	1.15	53.36	0.517	0.781	0.577	17.02	106.93
TFPOC [27] (WACV '24)	0.75	66.04	0.687	0.848	0.696	24.79	138.11
DAVE [23] (CVPR '24)	0.08	97.62	0.843	0.799	0.790	15.23	103.53

Table 2. Results on the **validation set** of FSC147 on both PrACo metrics (negative and mosaics tests) and on classic metrics.

Method	Negative Test		Mosaic Test			Classic	
	NMN ↓	PCCN ↑	CntP ↑	CntR ↑	CntF1 ↑	MAE ↓	RMSE ↓
CounTX [2] (BMVC '23)	0.87	69.79	0.664	0.658	0.579	17.27	66.37
CLIP-Count [14] (ACM MM '23)	1.24	48.11	0.488	0.702	0.522	18.90	66.75
VLCounter [15] (AAAI '24)	1.07	62.70	0.520	0.741	0.561	18.09	65.59
TFPOC [27] (WACV '24)	0.67	62.62	0.723	0.757	0.656	32.84	110.60
DAVE [23] (CVPR '24)	0.13	95.90	0.819	0.751	0.757	16.58	54.73

Figure 4. Boxplot showing the distribution of the correct count drifts of the different models. Despite the lower mean value, TFPOC and DAVE show a consistent number of outliers, revealing that they may catastrophically fail in some specific conditions.

CLIP-Count, and VLCounter shows that the average negative count is comparable to the ground-truth count of the correct class ($\text{NMN} \approx 1$), with CLIP-Count and VLCounter achieving $\text{NMN} > 1$. This trend is further confirmed by the PCCN metric, where CLIP-Count has the correct estimate nearer to the ground-truth only 38% of the times on the test set. Instead, the two-stage detectors TFPOC and DAVE achieve the best performance on the negative test. The same trends are mostly confirmed on the mosaic test. Specifically, while the CntR metric only increments by around 12% between the worst-performing method (CounTX) and the best-performing one (DAVE), the CntP shows a notable increase, from 0.517 of VLCounter to 0.843 of DAVE, which is an improvement of around 63%. This shows how the methods, despite being mostly able to count the correct

class, have a highly heterogeneous behavior with respect to the negative images within the mosaics. It is also worth noticing that more recent methods do not always improve on the PrACo metrics, meaning that this aspect is still largely underestimated. It is interesting to observe how TFPOC, a training-free model obtaining less competitive results on classic counting metrics, can instead defeat older learning-based CAC models on the proposed metrics.

Correct Count Drift. From the mosaic test, it is also interesting to understand how the various models drift the estimate about the positive class c_{ij}^{pos} when changing the negative image I_j . In other words, we would like to estimate the *confusion* of the model when it is requested to count a given class, but objects of another class are present in the image. In Fig. 4, we report, for each model, the distribution of the quantity $\left\{ \frac{|c_{ij}^{\text{pos}} - c_{ii}|}{c_{ii}} \right\}_{i,j=1}^N$, which encodes the normalized absolute error between the estimate of the model when only presented with the correct class as estimated in the negative test (c_{ii}) and the estimate of the model when presented with all the mosaics constructed with positive image I_i on the top (c_{ij}^{pos}). As we can notice, although DAVE achieves the lowest drift, it also presents many possibly problematic outliers. This may be due to the verification module, which incorrectly assigns the positive label to the cluster obtained from the objects from the negative image. Despite having a higher mean drift, the other methods – especially CounTX and CLIP-Count – show fewer outliers. This signifies that, although these methods wrongly count the negative classes,

Figure 5. This figure shows, for each model, the output density maps for three different (*mosaic, input prompt*) pairs. The count reported in the blue box is c_{ij}^{pos} , while the count reported in the dark orange box corresponds to c_{ij}^{neg} . We can notice how the models often misidentify instances from the negative image in the mosaic, though most accurately estimate the positive instances in the upper part.

the count relative to the positive part of the mosaic is less dependent on the number of negative instances from the bottom image of the mosaic. This insight further raises the attention to effective two-stage methods that, despite being very effective in discriminating the different classes, may catastrophically fail in some specific scenarios.

Qualitative Results. In Fig. 5, we show some qualitative results from the various methods examined through the lenses of the mosaic test. The lack of a proper understanding of the correct class to count is largely deducible from the reported density maps. While many methods correctly estimate the positive class on the top of the mosaics, most of the models give a non-zero count prediction of the negative instances from the negative images. We can notice how DAVE, in the first and last rows, correctly ignores the negative instances, exactly estimating zero objects. However, its second-stage verification approach may occasionally fail in a catastrophic manner, assigning the label to all the instances of the negative class, as shown in the second reported example. Although the mosaic test already gives many insights into the failure modes of the probed SOTA models, in the supplementary material, we also report some qualitative results from the negative test.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we introduced Prompt-Aware Counting (PrACo), a novel benchmark composed of two targeted test

suites specifically designed to address the limitations of current evaluation systems for prompt-based CAC.

Our evaluation of several recent state-of-the-art CAC methods revealed significant performance gaps, particularly in the ability of the models to handle negative and multi-class scenarios. While two-stage models like DAVE generally outperformed one-stage models on the negative test, they still exhibited notable weaknesses, particularly in the mosaic test, where they sometimes struggled with false positives from the negative images.

These findings suggest that SOTA models, despite their success on standard metrics, require more careful designs and better training procedures to improve their understanding of textual prompts. We hope PrACo provides a foundation for a more comprehensive evaluation and opens the door for developing more robust methods in the near future.

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